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FW Cixiidae: *Pintalia* sp.

HW Aphrophoridae: *Aphrophora* sp.

Already present cross-veins align to support wing margin (new "ambient vein" does not exist)

Cercopidae: *Tomaspis inca* Mexico

Field Museum

HW

WATCH IT! 2

HW Cercopidae: *Tomaspis inca* (Guer.) Mexico

Key to articulation

HW Cercopidae: *Tomaspis inca* (Guer.)
Honduras

crazy variability
5

Examples of variability

Cercopidae: *Tomaspis inca* Mexico

FW Ventral

FW Cercopidae: *Tomaspis inca*

HIGHLY VARIABLE ARTICULATION -
A STUDY of 6

Wildly derived. Better recheck other spp. to confirm ...

FW Cicadoidea, Cercopidae, *Mahamaina costaricensis*

Cicadomorpha: Cercopidae: *Mahanaina costaricensis*

HW

Sep sunk under R&MA

Cicadomorpha Siam

large, Gainesville, Fla

HW Cicadoidea: Cicadidae: *Tropha colorata*

Darwin Museum, Graham Brown

FW Cicadomorpha

Cicadomorpha

Siam

large, Gainesville, Fla

HW genus unknown

HW Cicadomorpha

Auchenorhyncha
 Cicadoidea
 Tettigarctidae: *Tettigarcta*

Tettigarctidae, *Tettigarcta*

HW

Tettigarcta

Cicadoidea: Tettigarctidae: *Tettigarcta*

Tettigarctidae: *Tettigarcta* sp.

HW Membracidae

length 16.10 mm width 12mm

Hemineoptera

Copidocephala merula

FW Eurybrachidae: *Dasudaba* sp. Darwin Museum, Australia
 Graham Brown

HW Eurybrachidae: *Dasudaba* Darwin Museum, Australia

HW Eurybrachidae: *Eurybrachis* sp. Darwin Museum, Australia

Fulgoromorpha: Eurybrachidae: *Eurybrachys* or *Platybrachys*

Australia

Flatidae: *Pseudoflatoides* sp.

Cuba

articulation wildly unusual, more research needed
plenty of reductions

FW Flatidae

Pseudoflatoides sp.

Cuba

Note: very large PR PC&C

Cut reduced

Cuba, Havana 29

Fulguroidea: Flatidae: *Siphanta acuta* Walker, aff.

Tulson, New Zealand

Anterior wing margin----- support

Fulgoroidea, Flatidae, *Ityraca nigrocineta*, S. Africa

cut through anterior wing margin
3 mm distally from wing base

Epipleuron is composed of PCA+ & PCP- (extended ventrad)
and of CA+

Cicadidae, *Pararagnia tumida*, S. Africa AA4+2

Fulgoromorpha, Fulgoridae, *Dasudaba* sp, (*danae*?) HW, Australia

Fulgoromorpha, Fulgoridae, *Dasudaba* sp. FW base and HW, Australia

Fulgoromorpha: Fulgoridae: *Dasudaba* sp. (danae?)

Australia
P

FW Fulgoridae

New Guinea and New Zealand

large, black, white spots

HW Fulgoridae

New Guinea

HW Fulgoromorpha: Fulgoridae: *Lanternaria* sp. Peanut Bug
 Zamorano, Honduras

Fulgoromorpha: Fulgoridae: *Phrictus quinquepartitus*

FW Cixiidae: *Pintalia* sp.

HW Aphrophoridae: *Aphrophora* sp.

Already present cross-veins align to support wing margin (new "ambient vein" does not exist)

Homoptera: Fulgoromorpha
FW Lophopidae

Australia, Ravenshoe

length 12mm